

MEASUREMENT OF STRENGTH, FREQUENCY AND PERIOD OF AC ELECTRICAL SIGNALS IN THE LABVIEW ENVIRONMENT

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Аннотация. Measuring the amplitude, frequency and period of various signals is important when mastering the subject “Theoretical Electrical Engineering”. The article analyzes the main parameters, types of periodic electrical signals, as well as measured parameters on the bench in the LabVIEW environment.

Аннотация. “Nazariy elektrotexnika” fanini o‘zlashtirishda turli signallarning amplitudasi, chastotasi va davrini o‘lchash muhim ahamiyatga ega. Maqolada davriy elektr signallarning asosiy parametrlari, turlari, hamda LabVIEW muhitida o‘lchovlar olib borish stenda tahlil qilingan.

Аннотация. Измерение амплитуды, частоты и периода различных сигналов важно при освоении предмета «Теоретическая электротехника». В статье анализируются основные параметры, виды периодических электрических сигналов, а также измеренных параметров на стенде в среде LabVIEW.

Learning to measure alternating current voltage, frequency, and period is important. In this article, the above parameters of alternating current are studied on virtual stands in the LabVIEW environment.

When sinusoidal alternating voltage is measured, its root mean square (effective) value is usually determined. When finding the value of the acting voltage U_a , it is connected with the value of the instantaneous voltage.

$$U_a \sqrt{\frac{1}{T} \int_0^T u^2(t) dt}$$

Here T is the alternating voltage period. The average rectified value is found by the arithmetic mean value of the absolute instantaneous voltage over time.

$$U_{cv} \sqrt{\frac{1}{T} \int_0^T u^2(t) dt}$$

The relationship between the signal amplitude and its root mean square value for the free form of periodic oscillations is determined by the following formula.

$$U_m = K_a * U_{CK}$$

Here, K_a is the amplitude coefficient. The relationship between the corrected mean and its root mean square value for the free form of periodic oscillations is determined by the following expression.

$$U_{ck} = K_f * U_{cv}$$

Here K_f is the form factor.

Description of the Lab Bench consists of a computer model of Lab VIEW on a computer display. The stand has a model of electromagnetic and electrodynamic voltmeters, an electronic voltmeter with an amplitude detector, an electronic millivoltmeter with a mean square value, an electronic oscillograph, and a special type of signal generator.

A model of a laboratory stand on a computer display

- 1- Electromagnetic voltmeter
- 2- Electrodynamic voltmeter
- 3- Electronic voltmeter with amplitude detector
- 4- Mean-smoothed mean-squared value
- 5- Electronic millivoltmeter
- 6- Electronic oscillograph
- 7- Special shape signal generator

The purpose of the work: to learn to measure the frequency and period of electric signals, to get acquainted with the equipment and types of frequency meters with electronic counters with resonant characteristics.

In practice, the determination of the frequency of electrical signals is determined from 0 hertz to 1011 hertz. Electromechanical devices are used at frequencies from 50 hertz to 400 hertz. Among them there are electromechanical frequency meters and analogue frequency meters. The error of analog electromechanical frequency meters is 1-2.5%.

Measurements in laboratory conditions are mainly carried out using an oscilloscope. Electronic capacitor frequency meters are used to measure frequencies from 10 hertz to 1 megahertz radius. The magnet consists of charging and de-energizing the capacitor from the battery through an electrical mechanism.

This process is carried out with a measurable frequency. Because charging and de-energizing are carried out under the influence of the studied voltage.

During one period, the power equal to $Q = CU$ passes through the magneto-electric mechanism. It follows that the average current flowing from the indicator is equal to $I_{medium} = Qf_x = CUf_x$.

Thus, the readings of the magnetic electric ammeter are proportional to the measured frequency.

The error of such frequency meters is around 2-3%.

The laboratory device (stand) consists of a computer model of Lab VIEW on a computer display. The device (stand) is equipped with resonant and digital frequency meters, a signal generator and switching equipment.

- 1- electronic digital frequency meter.
- 2- signal generator.
- 3- resonant frequency meter.
- 4- Switching equipment

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